

An update to the inventory of reef-fishes for Colombia's Caribbean mainland coast with a catalog of photographic vouchers

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Abstract

Between 20 June and 2 September 2023, Carlos Estapé (CJE) & Allison Morgan Estapé (AME) photo-documented reef fishes found along Colombia's Caribbean mainland coast, in and around Tayrona National Natural Park (Parque Nacional Natural Tayrona) and Rosario and San Bernardo Corals National Natural Park (Parque Nacional Natural Corales del Rosario y de San Bernardo) in the region around Cartagena and Santa Marta. Here we present our findings, which include in-situ underwater photo vouchers of 316 species. Thirteen species are first records for anywhere along Colombia's Caribbean mainland coast and voucher photographs are presented and 7 species were photographed underwater for the first time within their entire range in the Greater Caribbean.

Key words: ichthyology, coral-reef fishes, SCUBA surveys, photo vouchers, Tayrona National Natural Park, Parque Nacional Natural Tayrona, Rosario and San Bernardo Corals National Natural Park, georeferenced aggregator records

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Introduction

Colombia's Caribbean mainland coast stretches for about 1,770 km between its northwestern border with Panama and its eastern border with Venezuela (Fig. 1). Southwest of the coastal city of Cartagena and about 48 km offshore is the Rosario and San Bernardo Corals National Natural Park (Parque Nacional Natural Corales del Rosario y de San Bernardo, PNNCR) which encompass 194 square kilometers of marine habitat and includes a 30-island archipelago with coral reefs, mangroves, sandy bottoms and clear waters. Roughly 177 km northeast of Cartagena, near the coastal city of Santa Marta, is Tayrona National Natural Park (Parque Nacional Natural Tayrona, PNNT) which includes about 31 sq km of protected marine habitat consisting of coral reefs, rocky coastline, sandy bays, seagrass beds and mangroves (Fig. 2).

Between 20 June 2023 and 2 September 2023, CJE and AME photo-documented reef-fishes during 204 SCUBA dives at these two marine protected areas and at the entry to Cartagena Bay. They were joined for part of that time by D. Ross Robertson of the Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute (16 dives), Alasdair G. Dunlap-Smith underwater photographer (41 dives), Arturo Acero of CECIMAR (4 dives), Jose J. Tavera Vargas of Universidad del Valle, Cali (2 dives), and Rocío García Urueña of Universidad del Magdalena, Colombia (2 dives).

Photographs that are georeferenced and evaluated for taxonomic validity represent true vouchers for species-location records for scientific databases and can be used by scientists, managers, citizen scientists, recreational divers, and fishers who want to identify the fishes they see and catch, in the present case along Colombia's Caribbean mainland coast. During the course of this study as many reef-fish species as possible were photo-documented, some of which are new records for Caribbean Colombia and some of which were photographed in-situ for the first time anywhere in the Greater Caribbean.

Materials and Methods

The study included three survey areas (Fig. 2): (1) Tayrona National Natural Park (Parque Nacional Natural Tayrona, PNNT) and environs which includes dive sites off Taganga, Santa Marta and Rodadero to the southwest; (2) Cartagena, and (3) Isla Grande in the Rosario and San Bernardo Corals National Natural Park (Parque Nacional Natural Corales del Rosario y de San Bernardo, PNNCR).

Figure 1. Map of Greater Caribbean with Caribbean Colombia region highlighted (courtesy D.R. Robertson, Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute, <https://biogeodb.stri.si.edu/caribbean/en/pages/generalinfo>).

Figure 1. Map of Caribbean Colombia region with national parks in green, stars indicate the three study sites (map courtesy <https://www.natureearthdata.com>, revised and annotated).

TABLE 1

Summary of Survey Dives			
	# Dive Sites	# Dives	Study Period
Total for all areas surveyed	59	204	6/20 – 9/2/2023
Tayrona National Park & environs	47	170	6/20 – 8/17/2023
Tayrona National Park (PNNT)	36	146	6/20 – 8/17/2023
Taganga & Santa Marta	9	20	6/20 – 8/17/2023
Rodadero	2	4	7/14/2023
Cartagena	4	10	8/21 – 24/2023
Isla Grande, Rosario Islands (PNNCR)	8	24	8/26 – 9/2/2023

A total of 59 dive sites were surveyed on 204 dives, with the majority occurring within Tayrona National Natural Park and environs (Table 1). The habitats surveyed included open water, deep reefs, sloping walls, offshore and shallow reefs, mangroves, bays, muddy-sand bottoms, seagrass beds, river openings, channels, rocky and rubble bottoms, rock walls, crevasses, and shallow caves at depths ranging from 0 to 39.9 meters.

Supplemental Files 1, 2, 3, 5 & 6 datasets at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16951671>

Supplemental File #1 provides detailed dive-site maps, dive-site names, georeferenced coordinates, and the number of dives.

Supplemental File #2 provides a detailed dive log for each of the 204 dives with site specific details, notable sightings and comments, and a summary of the number of dives per site and survey area.

Photographic tools included Canon 5D Mark IV cameras, Ikelite housings and strobes, and a GoPro 11. All images were processed in Adobe Lightroom Classic for cropping, white balance, tone, presence and sharpening.

The focus was on photo-documenting all fish species seen within Tayrona National Natural Park (PNNT) and supplementing that effort in the other areas with images of species not photographed in PNNT. During this survey, a library of 5,751 images was compiled by CJE and AME and are all viewable by following the links in Table 2. Each image's georeferenced location can be determined by cross-referencing the image's metadata with the detailed dive log in Supplemental File #2.

Sources of location data on species occurrences for the species photo-documented in the three areas during this survey were compared to georeferenced records in 4 major online data aggregators: GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility, OBIS (Ocean Biodiversity Information System), SIAM (Sistema de Información Ambiental Marina) and Shorefishes of the Greater Caribbean: online information system (Robertson & Van Tassell 2024). In addition, they were also compared to occurrences in local published checklists of reef fishes from various sites

TABLE 2

Image Library

	# Images	Website address
Total in study area	5751	
Tayrona National Park	5027	https://carloestape.photoshelter.com/gallery/Colombia-Cartagena/G0000rzT8cRQ_mak/
Cartagena	213	https://carloestape.photoshelter.com/gallery/Colombia-Isla-Grande-del-Rosario/G00009MagVKS8u6I/
Isla Grande, Rosario Islands	511	https://carloestape.photoshelter.com/gallery/Colombia-Tayrona/G0000zKiLUHpfBE/

on the continental coast of Colombia: Garzón & Acero (1983); Acero et al. (1984); Acero & Garzón (1985, 1986, 1987a, 1987b, 2016); Reyes-Nivia et al. (2004); Olaya-Restrepo et al. (2008); Grijalba-Bendeck et al. (2017); Chasqui Velasco & Gonzalez Corredor (2019); Escobar Sierra et al. (2021); and Carvalho Filho et al. (2022).

Scientific names of species used in this paper, based on the names in Eschmeyer’s Catalog of Fishes (Fricke et al. 2024), that differ from names used by SIAM (2024) and the referenced publications above are listed for 39 species documented during this survey (see **Supplemental File #3**).

Results

A total of 316 fish species were photo-documented within the survey area, with 281 from Parque Nacional Natural Tayrona and environs, 55 species at Cartagena, and 80 species at Parque Nacional Natural Los Corales del Rosario y de San Bernardo (Table 3, at end of article). Photographic voucher plates for each species are provided in **Supplemental File #4** at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16951568>

Thirteen species are newly documented records for anywhere along the Caribbean continental coast of Colombia and their voucher photographs are presented at the end of this text (Figs. 1–13), along with the distinguishing characteristics that separate them from related species. Although some of these species are mentioned in Acero et al.’s (2023) list of Caribbean Colombian fishes in GBIF, that list does not indicate where each species is found (on the continental coast vs. the offshore Colombian islands and reefs of the Seaflower Reserve) and is lacking georeferenced location records. Table 4 lists the new records and the survey areas where they were photo-documented. **Supplemental File #5** provides the georeferenced coordinates of the sites where each species was photo-documented.

Range extension updates are listed in **Supplemental File #6** for species not yet documented on Colombia’s Caribbean mainland coast in three major georeferenced-data aggregators: 49 species not listed in Global Biodiversity

TABLE 4

New species records for the Caribbean continental coast of Colombia (13)

location of photo vouchers: T = Tayrona National Natural Park & environs, IR = Islas del Rosario, C = Cartagena

Family	Species	Common Name	Location
APOGONIDAE	<i>Apogon robbyi</i>	Striped Cardinalfish	T
CHAENOPSIDAE	<i>Emblemaria aff. australis</i>	Southern Shortfin Blenny	T
	<i>Emblemariopsis leptocirris</i>	Fine-cirris Blenny	T, IR
GOBIIDAE	<i>Coryphopterus kuna</i>	Kuna Goby	T, IR
	<i>Coryphopterus venezuelae</i>	Venezuela Goby	T, C
	<i>Ctenogobius stigmaturus</i>	Spottail Goby	T
	<i>Tigrigobius zebrellus</i>	Zebrette Goby	T
KYPHOSIDAE	<i>Kyphosus cinerascens</i>	Topsail Seachub	T
LABRIDAE: SCARINAE	<i>Sparisoma griseorubrum</i>	Grey Parrotfish	T
LABRISOMIDAE	<i>Starksia robertsoni</i>	Southwest Blackcheek Shy Blenny	IR
OPHICHTHIDAE	<i>Echiophis intertinctus</i>	Spotted Spoon-nose Eel	T
SERRANIDAE	<i>Schultzea beta</i>	School Bass	T
TRIPTERYGIIDAE	<i>Enneanectes deloachorum</i>	Two-bar Triplefin	T, IR

Information Facility (GBIF 2024) as of 15 March 2024, 33 species in Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS 2024) as of 15 March 2024 and 38 species in the Sistema de Información Ambiental Marina (SIAM 2024) as of 9 June 2024.

Seven species were photographed live, underwater, in-situ for the first time within their known geographic ranges (Figs. 14–17).

Conclusions

This study increased our knowledge of the size of the reef-fish fauna off Colombia's mainland coast, photo-vouchered 316 species with georeferenced locations and extended the known geographic range for 13 species into the Colombian Caribbean. The first live underwater images of 7 species documents their living colors and permits detailed comparisons with similar congeners. The information obtained will be especially useful to scientists, citizen scientists, naturalists, and recreational divers, as well as fishery and park managers and fishers, to identify fishes they observe or catch along Colombia's Caribbean mainland coast.

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New records for the Colombian mainland Caribbean fauna (in family alphabetic order)

Apogon robbyi Gilbert & Tyler, 1997: Striped Cardinalfish, cardenal rayado (Apogonidae)

Distinguishing characteristics: a small cardinalfish with a translucent red to reddish-brown body with yellow fins and about 10 thin dark stripes along the body, and a diffuse dark spot at the caudal-fin base.

Figure 1. *Apogon robbyi*, Tayrona National Park, Colombia.

Emblemaria aff. *australis* Ramos, Rocha & Rocha, 2003: Southern Sailfin Blenny, tubícola bandera del sur (Chaenopsidae)

Distinguishing characteristics: an elongated hole-dwelling blenny with males developing an elongated first dorsal-fin spine with a short orange segment just above the base, followed by a series of dark-and-cream bars becoming fainter along the length of the spine. The upper body has a series of 8 irregular brown bars, those on the front half of the body are usually more distinct.

Figure 2. *Emblemaria* aff. *australis*, Tayrona National Park, Colombia.

Emblemariopsis leptocirris Stephens, 1970: Fine-cirrus Blenny, tubícola de cirro fino (Chaenopsidae)

Distinguishing characteristics: an elongated hole-dwelling blenny with breeding males developing a black head, sometimes with scattered white spots; the first dorsal-fin spine has a white anterior margin, the remaining fin is dark. Non-breeding males and females have a translucent body with red, orange, and pink markings. Juveniles have a spike-like elevation of the first three dorsal-fin spines with dark and light bands. All stages have a short single orbital cirrus.

Figure 3. *Emblemariopsis leptocirris*, lower left, Isla Grande; top left and right pair, Tayrona National Park, Colombia.

Coryphopterus kuna Victor, 2007: Kuna Goby, gobio kuna (Gobiidae)

Distinguishing characteristics: a tiny translucent goby with scattered brown and orange irregular spots, and a larger dark patch over the abdomen. There is a linear row of small discrete black spots across the upper eyeball.

Figure 4. *Coryphopterus kuna*, top pair, Tayrona National Park; lower pair, Isla Grande, Colombia.

Coryphopterus venezuelae Cervigon, 1966: Venezuela Goby, gobio venezolano (Gobiidae)

Distinguishing characteristics: a mostly translucent goby with scattered white, bluish, and orange spots, and an orange and white stripe (bridle) below the eye. A diagnostic oval orange or dark spot is prominent on the lower half of the pectoral-fin base.

Figure 5. *Coryphopterus venezuelae*, left, Cartagena; right, Tayrona National Park, Colombia.

Ctenogobius stigmaturus (Goode & Bean, 1882): Spottail Goby, gobio cola marcada (Gobiidae)

Distinguishing characteristics: an elongated goby covered with irregular brown spots and blotches. The lower rim of the preoperculum has a dark crescent mark followed by a dark patch on the mid-operculum. Dark lateral-midline oval patches extend along the flanks, often comma-shaped.

Figure 6. *Ctenogobius stigmaturus*, Tayrona National Park, Colombia.

Tigrigobius zebrellus (Robins, 1958): Zebrette Goby, gobio cebra (Gobiidae)

Distinguishing characteristics: a small goby with the head and body translucent with distinctive, uniformly spaced, brown-to-black bars, varying in thickness. There are large internal black patches over the abdomen and black and white patches spaced along the vertebral column.

Figure 7a. *Tigrigobius zebrellus*, Tayrona National Park, Colombia.

Figure 7b. *Tigrigobius zebrellus*, Tayrona National Park, Colombia.

Kyphosus cinerascens (Forsskal, 1775): Topsail Seachub, chop aletialta (Kyphosidae)

Distinguishing characteristics: a chub with a relatively short, pointed, and beak-like snout, frequently with a hump on the snout before the eye. The dorsal and anal fins are high, and the anal fin is notably angular in outline.

Figure 8. *Kyphosus cinerascens*, Tayrona National Park, Colombia.

Sparisoma griseorubrum Cervigon, 1970: Grey Parrotfish, loro gris (Labridae: Scarinae)

Distinguishing characteristics: a large and stout parrotfish; the initial phase has a dark reddish-to-mottled body and reddish fins and a white to yellow triangular bar on the caudal peduncle. Terminal-phase males are dusky or shaded orangish to greenish or bluish, with a bright orange iris, blue reticulations on the head, and a pale caudal peduncle. Both phases have a distinct dark spot at the upper pectoral-fin base.

Figure 9. *Sparisoma griseorubrum*, top pair IP; lower pair TP, Tayrona National Park, Colombia.

Starksia robertsoni Baldwin, Victor & Castillo, 2011: Southwest Blackcheek Shy Blenny, trambollito tímido mejillas negras del suroeste (Labrisomidae)

Distinguishing characteristics: a tiny blenny with a mottled reddish head and body, without prominent bars or stripes; the head has single orbital cirri banded with white and short, unbranched, single, white nuchal cirri. Males have a blackened lower opercular rim and lips with white markings, but no scattering of round white spots on the upper lip.

Figure 10. *Starksia robertsoni*, Islas del Rosario, Colombia.

Echiophis intertinctus (Richardson, 1848): Spotted Spoon-nose Eel, tieso cucharón manchado (Ophichthidae)

Distinguishing characteristics: a stout-bodied large snake eel with a finely speckled head and large, rounded, irregular spots in three indistinct rows along the body.

Figure 11. *Echiophis intertinctus*, Tayrona National Park, Colombia.

Schultzea beta (Hildebrand, 1940): School Bass, serrano escolar (Serranidae)

Distinguishing characteristics: a small, slim, schooling bass with large eyes, a pale orangish head and body, shading to yellow posteriorly and indistinct lateral dark or orange stripes and no black spots or bars on the body or fins.

Figure 12. *Schultzea beta*, Tayrona National Park, Colombia.

Enneanectes deloachorum Victor, 2013: Two-Bar Triplefin, tres aletas dos barras (Tripterygiidae)

Distinguishing characteristics: a snub-nosed blenny with three separated dorsal fins, the first shorter and often whitish. The body has a series of dark bars becoming darker posteriorly, with the last two darkest (to varying degrees) and divided by a bright white intervening bar without a central dark patch. The caudal fin has a narrow white band followed by a wide dark bar.

Figure 13. *Enneanectes deloachorum*, top right, Isla Grande; left pair and lower right, Tayrona National Park, Colombia.

First underwater photographs of a Caribbean fish species (in family alphabetic order)

Figure 14. *Emblemaria* aff. *australis*, Southern Sailfin Blenny, Tayrona National Park, Colombia.

Figure 15. *Gobiosoma spilotum*, Isthmian Goby (left) and *Priolepis robinsi*, Tayrona Goby (right); Tayrona National Park, Colombia.

Figure 16. *Starksia robertsoni*, Southwest Blackcheek Shy Blenny (left) and *Starksia variabilis*, Variable Blenny (right); Islas del Rosario, Colombia.

Figure 17. *Myrophis anterodorsalis*, Longfin Worm Eel (left) and *Ophichthus cylindroideus*, Tentacle-nose Eel (right); Tayrona National Park, Colombia.

TABLE 3

List of 316 fishes photo-documented from the mainland Colombian Caribbean region

Latin Name	Common Name	Plate	Tayrona NP (281)	Cartagena (55)	Rosario (80)
ACANTHURIDAE					
<i>Acanthurus chirurgus</i>	Doctorfish	P1	1		
<i>Acanthurus coeruleus</i>	Blue Tang	P1	1		
<i>Acanthurus tractus</i>	Northern Ocean Surgeonfish	P1	1		
ACHIRIDAE					
<i>Gymnachirus nudus</i>	Flabby Sole	P1			1
AETOBATIDAE					
<i>Aetobatus narinari</i>	Spotted Eagle Ray	P1			1
ANTENNARIIDAE					
<i>Antennarius multiocellatus</i>	Longlure Frogfish	P1	1		
<i>Antennarius scaber</i>	Striated Frogfish	P1	1		
APOGONIDAE					
<i>Apogon lachneri</i>	Whitestar Cardinalfish	P1	1		
<i>Apogon maculatus</i>	Flamefish	P1	1		
<i>Apogon pillionatus</i>	Broadsaddle Cardinalfish	P1	1		
<i>Apogon planifrons</i>	Pale Cardinalfish	P1		1	
<i>Apogon pseudomaculatus</i>	Twospot Cardinalfish	P1	1		
<i>Apogon robbyi</i>	Striped Cardinalfish	P1	1		
<i>Apogon robinsi</i>	Roughlip Cardinalfish	P1	1		
<i>Apogon townsendi</i>	Belted Cardinalfish	P1	1		
<i>Paroncheilus affinis</i>	Bigtooth Cardinalfish	P1	1		
<i>Phaeoptyx conklini</i>	Freckled Cardinalfish	P1	1		
<i>Phaeoptyx pigmentaria</i>	Dusky Cardinalfish	P1	1		
ATHERINIDAE					
<i>Atherinomorus stipes</i>	Hardhead Silverside	P1	1		1
AULOSTOMIDAE					
<i>Aulostomus maculatus</i>	Atlantic Trumpetfish	P1	1		
BALISTIDAE					
<i>Balistes capriscus</i>	Gray Triggerfish	P2	1		
<i>Balistes vetula</i>	Queen Triggerfish	P2	1		
<i>Canthidermis sufflamen</i>	Ocean Triggerfish	P2			1
BATRACHOIDIDAE					
<i>Thalassophryne maculosa</i>	Caño Toadfish	P2	1		
BELONIDAE					
<i>Platybelone argalus argalus</i>	Keeltail Needlefish	P2	1		
<i>Tylosurus crocodilus</i>	Houndfish	P2	1		
BLENNIIDAE					
<i>Entomacrodus nigricans</i>	Pearl Blenny	P2	1		1
<i>Hypleurochilus pseudoaequipinnis</i>	Oyster Blenny	P2	1		
<i>Hypleurochilus springeri</i>	Orangespotted Blenny	P2			1
<i>Hypsoblennius invemar</i>	Tessellated Blenny	P2	1		
<i>Ophioblennius macclurei</i>	Redlip Blenny	P2	1		1
<i>Parablennius marmoratus</i>	Seaweed Blenny	P2	1		
<i>Scartella cristata</i>	Molly Miller	P2	1	1	
BOTHIDAE					
<i>Bothus lunatus</i>	Peacock Flounder	P2	1		

<i>Bothus maculiferus</i>	Mottled Flounder	P2	1	1	
<i>Bothus ocellatus</i>	Eyed Flounder	P2	1		1
BYTHITIDAE					
<i>Stygnobrotula latebricola</i>	Black Brotula	P2	1		
CALLIONYMIDAE					
<i>Callionymus bairdi</i>	Lancer Dragonet	P2	1		
CARANGIDAE					
<i>Caranx bartholomaei</i>	Yellow Jack	P2	1	1	
<i>Caranx crysos</i>	Blue Runner	P2	1		1
<i>Caranx hippos</i>	Crevalle Jack	P2		1	
<i>Caranx latus</i>	Horse-eye Jack	P2	1		
<i>Caranx ruber</i>	Bar Jack	P2	1		
<i>Chloroscombrus chrysurus</i>	Atlantic Bumper	P2			1
<i>Decapterus macarellus</i>	Mackerel Scad	P3	1		
<i>Decapterus punctatus</i>	Round Scad	P3	1		
<i>Elagatis bipinnulata</i>	Rainbow Runner	P3	1		1
<i>Oligoplites saurus saurus</i>	Leatherjack	P3	1		1
<i>Selar crumenophthalmus</i>	Bigeye Scad	P3	1		
<i>Seriola rivoliana</i>	Almaco Jack	P3	1		
<i>Trachinotus goodei</i>	Palometa	P3	1		
CHAENOPSIDAE					
<i>Acanthemblemaria aceroi</i>	Blue-dotted Tube Blenny	P3	1		
<i>Acanthemblemaria aspera</i>	Roughhead Blenny	P3		1	1
<i>Acanthemblemaria betinensis</i>	Speckled Blenny	P3	1	1	1
<i>Acanthemblemaria rivasi</i>	Spotjaw Blenny	P3			1
<i>Chaenopsis limbaughii</i>	Yellowface Pikeblenny	P3	1		1
<i>Coralliozetus cardonae</i>	Twinhorn Blenny	P3	1		
<i>Emblemaria aff. australis</i>	Southern shortfin Blenny	P3	1		
<i>Emblemaria pandionis</i>	Sailfin Blenny	P3	1		
<i>Emblemariopsis leptocirris</i>	Fine-cirrus Blenny	P3	1		1
<i>Emblemariopsis tayrona</i>	Tayrona Blenny	P3	1		
<i>Lucayablennius zingaro</i>	Arrow Blenny	P3			1
CHAETODONTIDAE					
<i>Chaetodon capistratus</i>	Foureye Butterflyfish	P3	1		
<i>Chaetodon ocellatus</i>	Spotfin Butterflyfish	P3	1	1	
<i>Chaetodon sedentarius</i>	Reef Butterflyfish	P3	1		
<i>Chaetodon striatus</i>	Banded Butterflyfish	P3	1		
<i>Prognathodes aculeatus</i>	Longsnout Butterflyfish	P3	1		
CIRRHITIDAE					
<i>Amblycirrhitus pinos</i>	Redspotted Hawkfish	P3	1		
CLUPEIDAE					
<i>Harengula humeralis</i>	Redear Sardine	P4	1		1
<i>Opisthonema oglinum</i>	Atlantic Thread Herring	P4	1		
<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	Spanish Sardine	P4	1		
CONGRIDAE					
<i>Ariosoma balearicum</i>	Bandtooth Conger	P4		1	
<i>Heteroconger longissimus</i>	Brown Garden Eel	P4	1	1	
DACTYLOPTERIDAE					
<i>Dactylopterus volitans</i>	Flying Gurnard	P4	1		
DIODONTIDAE					
<i>Chilomycterus antennatus</i>	Bridled Burrfish	P4		1	

<i>Chilomycterus antillarum</i>	Web Burrfish	P4	1		
<i>Diodon holocanthus</i>	Balloonfish	P4	1		
<i>Diodon hystrix</i>	Porcupinefish	P4	1		
ECHENEIDAE					
<i>Echeneis naucrates</i>	Sharksucker	P4	1		
EPHIPPIDAE					
<i>Chaetodipterus faber</i>	Atlantic Spadefish	P4	1		
FISTULARIIDAE					
<i>Fistularia petimba</i>	Red Cornetfish	P4	1		
<i>Fistularia tabacaria</i>	Bluespotted Cornetfish	P4	1		
GERREIDAE					
<i>Diapterus rhombeus</i>	Rhombic Mojarra	P4			1
<i>Eucinostomus argenteus</i>	Spotfin Mojarra	P4	1		
<i>Eucinostomus gula</i>	Silver Jenny	P4	1		
<i>Eucinostomus jonesii</i>	Slender Mojarra	P4	1		
<i>Eucinostomus melanopterus</i>	Flagfin Mojarra	P4	1		
<i>Gerres cinereus</i>	Yellowfin Mojarra	P4	1		1
GOBIESOCIDAE					
<i>Acyrtus rubiginosus</i>	Red Clingfish	P4	1		
<i>Gobiesox punctulatus</i>	Stippled Clingfish	P4	1		
GOBIIDAE					
<i>Barbulifer ceuthoecus</i>	Bearded Goby	P4	1		
<i>Bollmannia boqueronensis</i>	White-eye Goby	P5	1		
<i>Coryphopterus dicrus</i>	Colon Goby	P5	1	1	1
<i>Coryphopterus eidolon</i>	Pallid Goby	P5	1		1
<i>Coryphopterus glaucofraenum</i>	Bridled Goby	P5	1	1	1
<i>Coryphopterus hyalinus</i>	Glass Goby	P5	1		1
<i>Coryphopterus kuna</i>	Kuna Goby	P5	1		1
<i>Coryphopterus lipernes</i>	Peppermint Goby	P5	1		
<i>Coryphopterus personatus</i>	Masked Goby	P5	1		1
<i>Coryphopterus thrix</i>	Bartail Goby	P5	1		
<i>Coryphopterus venezuelae</i>	Venezuela Goby	P5	1	1	
<i>Ctenogobius boleosoma</i>	Darter Goby	P5	1		
<i>Ctenogobius saepepallens</i>	Dash Goby	P5	1	1	
<i>Ctenogobius stigmaturus</i>	Spottail Goby	P5	1		
<i>Elacatinus horsti</i>	Yellowline Goby	P5			1
<i>Elacatinus illecebrosus</i>	Barsnout Goby	P5	1	1	1
<i>Gnatholepis thompsoni</i>	Goldspot Goby	P5	1	1	
<i>Gobionellus oceanicus</i>	Highfin Goby	P5	1		
<i>Gobiosoma spilotum</i>	Isthmian Goby	P5	1		
<i>Lophogobius cyprinoides</i>	Crested Goby	P5			1
<i>Lythrypnus elasson</i>	Dwarf Goby	P5	1		
<i>Lythrypnus minimus</i>	Pygmy Goby	P5		1	1
<i>Microgobius carri</i>	Seminole Goby	P5	1		
<i>Microgobius meeki</i>	Meek's Goby	P5	1		
<i>Microgobius signatus</i>	Signal Goby	P5	1		
<i>Nes longus</i>	Orangespotted Goby	P5	1	1	
<i>Oxyurichthys stigmalocephus</i>	Spotfin Goby	P5	1	1	
<i>Priolepis hipoliti</i>	Rusty Goby	P5	1		
<i>Priolepis robinsi</i>	Tayrona Goby	P5	1		
<i>Ptereleotris helenae</i>	Hovering Dartfish	P6	1	1	

<i>Risor ruber</i>	Tusked Goby	P6			1
<i>Tigrigobius dilepis</i>	Orangesided Goby	P6			1
<i>Tigrigobius pallens</i>	Semiscaled Goby	P6			1
<i>Tigrigobius panamensis</i>	Panamanian Greenbanded Goby	P6		1	
<i>Tigrigobius saucrus</i>	Leopard Goby	P6	1		1
<i>Tigrigobius zebrellus</i>	Zebrette Goby	P6	1		
GRAMMATIDAE					
<i>Gramma loreto</i>	Fairy Basslet	P6			1
<i>Gramma melacara</i>	Blackcap Basslet	P6			1
HAEMULIDAE					
<i>Anisotremus surinamensis</i>	Black Margate	P6	1		
<i>Anisotremus virginicus</i>	Porkfish	P6	1	1	
<i>Brachygenys chrysargyrea</i>	Smallmouth Grunt	P6	1		
<i>Emmelichthyops atlanticus</i>	The Bonnetmouth	P6	1	1	1
<i>Haemulon atlanticus</i>	Latin Grunt	P6	1		
<i>Haemulon aurolineatum</i>	Tomtate	P6	1		
<i>Haemulon carbonarium</i>	Caesar Grunt	P6	1		
<i>Haemulon flavolineatum</i>	French Grunt	P6	1	1	1
<i>Haemulon macrostoma</i>	Spanish Grunt	P6	1		
<i>Haemulon melanurum</i>	Cottonwick	P6	1		
<i>Haemulon plumierii</i>	White Grunt	P6	1		
<i>Haemulon striatum</i>	Striped Grunt	P6	1		1
<i>Haemulon vittatum</i>	Boga	P6	1		
<i>Paranisotremus moricandi</i>	the Burro	P6	1		
HOLOCENTRIDAE					
<i>Holocentrus adscensionis</i>	Squirrelfish	P6	1		
<i>Holocentrus rufus</i>	Longspine Squirrelfish	P6	1		1
<i>Myripristis jacobus</i>	Blackbar Soldierfish	P6	1	1	
<i>Neoniphon marianus</i>	Longjaw Squirrelfish	P6	1		
<i>Neoniphon vexillarium</i>	Dusky Squirrelfish	P6	1		
<i>Plectrypops retrospinis</i>	Cardinal Soldierfish	P7	1		
KYPHOSIDAE					
<i>Kyphosus cinerascens</i>	Topsail Seachub	P7	1		
<i>Kyphosus vaigiensis</i>	Yellow Chub	P7	1		
LABRIDAE LABRINAE					
<i>Bodianus pulchellus</i>	Spotfin Hogfish	P7	1		
<i>Bodianus rufus</i>	Spanish Hogfish	P7	1		
<i>Clepticus parrae</i>	Creole Wrasse	P7	1		1
<i>Halichoeres bivittatus</i>	Slippery Dick	P7	1		
<i>Halichoeres cyanocephalus</i>	Yellowcheek Wrasse	P7	1		
<i>Halichoeres garnoti</i>	Yellowhead Wrasse	P7	1		
<i>Halichoeres maculipinna</i>	Clown Wrasse	P7	1		
<i>Halichoeres pictus</i>	Rainbow Wrasse	P7	1		
<i>Halichoeres poeyi</i>	Blackear Wrasse	P7	1	1	
<i>Halichoeres radiatus</i>	Puddingwife	P7	1		1
<i>Lachnolaimus maximus</i>	Hogfish	P7	1		
<i>Thalassoma bifasciatum</i>	Bluehead	P7	1		
<i>Xyrichtys martinicensis</i>	Rosy Razorfish	P7	1		
<i>Xyrichtys novacula</i>	Pearly Razorfish	P7	1	1	
<i>Xyrichtys splendens</i>	Green Razorfish	P7	1		

LABRIDAE SCARINAE

<i>Cryptotomus roseus</i>	Bluelip Parrotfish	P7	1		
<i>Nicholsina usta</i>	Emerald Parrotfish	P7	1		
<i>Scarus guacamaia</i>	Rainbow Parrotfish	P7	1	1	1
<i>Scarus iseri</i>	Striped Parrotfish	P7	1		
<i>Scarus taeniopterus</i>	Princess Parrotfish	P7	1		
<i>Scarus vetula</i>	Queen Parrotfish	P7	1		
<i>Sparisoma atomarium</i>	Greenblotch Parrotfish	P7	1		
<i>Sparisoma aurofrenatum</i>	Redband Parrotfish	P7	1		
<i>Sparisoma chrysopterus</i>	Redtail Parrotfish	P7	1		
<i>Sparisoma griseorubrum</i>	Grey Parrotfish	P7	1		
<i>Sparisoma radians</i>	Bucktooth Parrotfish	P8	1		
<i>Sparisoma rubripinne</i>	Yellowtail Parrotfish	P8	1		
<i>Sparisoma viride</i>	Stoplight Parrotfish	P8	1		

LABRISOMIDAE

<i>Brockius albigenys</i>	Whitecheek Blenny	P8			1
<i>Gobioclinus guppyi</i>	Mimic Blenny	P8			1
<i>Labrisomus nuchipinnis</i>	Hairy Blenny	P8	1	1	
<i>Malacoctenus triangulatus</i>	Saddled Blenny	P8		1	1
<i>Paraclinus fasciatus</i>	Banded Blenny	P8	1		
<i>Starksia nanodes</i>	Dwarf Blenny	P8			1
<i>Starksia robertsoni</i>	Robertson's Blenny	P8			1
<i>Starksia variabilis</i>	Variable Blenny	P8			1

LUTJANIDAE

<i>Lutjanus analis</i>	Mutton Snapper	P8	1		
<i>Lutjanus apodus</i>	Schoolmaster	P8	1		
<i>Lutjanus buccanella</i>	Blackfin Snapper	P8	1	1	
<i>Lutjanus griseus</i>	Gray Snapper	P8	1		1
<i>Lutjanus jocu</i>	Dog Snapper	P8	1		
<i>Lutjanus mahogoni</i>	Mahogany Snapper	P8	1		
<i>Lutjanus purpureus</i>	Caribbean Red Snapper	P8	1		
<i>Lutjanus synagris</i>	Lane Snapper	P8	1		1
<i>Ocyurus chrysurus</i>	Yellowtail Snapper	P8		1	
<i>Rhomboplites aurorubens</i>	Vermilion Snapper	P8			1

MALACANTHIDAE

<i>Malacanthus plumieri</i>	Sand Tilefish	P8	1	1	
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MONACANTHIDAE

<i>Aluterus scriptus</i>	Scrawled Filefish	P8	1		
<i>Cantherhines macrocerus</i>	Whitespotted Filefish	P8	1		
<i>Cantherhines pullus</i>	Orangespotted Filefish	P8	1		
<i>Monacanthus ciliatus</i>	Fringed Filefish	P8	1		
<i>Monacanthus tuckeri</i>	Slender Filefish	P8	1		
<i>Stephanolepis hispida</i>	Planehead Filefish	P8	1		

MUGILIDAE

<i>Mugil curema</i>	White Mullet	P9	1		
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MULLIDAE

<i>Mulloidichthys martinicus</i>	Yellow Goatfish	P9	1		
<i>Pseudupeneus maculatus</i>	Spotted Goatfish	P9	1		

MURAEINIDAE

<i>Echidna catenata</i>	Chain Moray	P9	1		1
<i>Enchelycore carychroa</i>	Chestnut Moray	P9	1		1

<i>Enchelycore nigricans</i>	Viper Moray	P9	1		
<i>Gymnothorax conspersus</i>	Saddled Moray	P9	1		
<i>Gymnothorax funebris</i>	Green Moray	P9	1	1	
<i>Gymnothorax miliaris</i>	Goldentail Moray	P9	1		1
<i>Gymnothorax moringa</i>	Spotted Moray	P9	1		
<i>Gymnothorax ocellatus</i>	Ocellated Moray	P9	1		
<i>Gymnothorax vicinus</i>	Purplemouth Moray	P9	1	1	1
MYLIOBATIDAE					
<i>Narcine bancroftii</i>	Lesser Electric Ray	P9	1	1	
OGCOEPHALIDAE					
<i>Ogcocephalus nasutus</i>	Shortnose Batfish	P9	1		
OPHICHTHIDAE					
<i>Echiophis intertinctus</i>	Spotted Spoon-nose Eel	P9	1		
<i>Echiophis punctifer</i>	Stippled spoon-nose eel	P9	1		
<i>Myrichthys breviceps</i>	Sharptail Eel	P9	1		
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted Eel	P9	1		
<i>Myrophis anterodorsalis</i>	Longfin Worm Eel	P9	1		
<i>Ophichthus cylindroideus</i>	Tentacle-nose Snake-eel	P9	1		
<i>Ophichthus ophis</i>	Spotted Snake Eel	P9	1		
OPISTOGNATHIDAE					
<i>Opistognathus aurifrons</i>	Yellowhead Jawfish	P9	1		
<i>Opistognathus macrognathus</i>	Banded Jawfish	P9	1		
<i>Opistognathus whitehursti</i>	Dusky Jawfish	P9	1		
OSTRACIIDAE					
<i>Acanthostracion polygonium</i>	Honeycomb Cowfish	P10	1		
<i>Acanthostracion quadricornis</i>	Scrawled Cowfish	P10	1		1
<i>Lactophrys bicaudalis</i>	Spotted Trunkfish	P10	1		
<i>Lactophrys triqueter</i>	Smooth Trunkfish	P10	1		
PARALICHTHYIDAE					
<i>Paralichthys tropicus</i>	Tropical Flounder	P10	1		
<i>Syacium micrurum</i>	Channel Flounder	P10	1		1
PEMPHERIDAE					
<i>Pempheris poeyi</i>	Shortfin Sweeper	P10	1		
<i>Pempheris schomburgkii</i>	Glassy Sweeper	P10	1		
POMACANTHIDAE					
<i>Centropyge argi</i>	Cherubfish	P10	1		
<i>Holacanthus ciliaris</i>	Queen Angelfish	P10	1		1
<i>Holacanthus tricolor</i>	Rock Beauty	P10	1		
<i>Pomacanthus arcuatus</i>	Gray Angelfish	P10	1		
<i>Pomacanthus paru</i>	French Angelfish	P10	1		
POMACENTRIDAE					
<i>Abudefduf saxatilis</i>	Sergeant Major	P10	1		
<i>Abudefduf taurus</i>	Night Sergeant	P10	1		
<i>Azurina cyanea</i>	Blue Chromis	P10	1		
<i>Azurina multilineata</i>	Brown Chromis	P10	1		
<i>Chromis insolata</i>	Sunshinefish	P10	1		
<i>Chromis scotti</i>	Purple Reeffish	P10	1		
<i>Chromis vanbeberae</i>	Whitetail Reeffish	P10	1		
<i>Microspathodon chrysurus</i>	Yellowtail Damselfish	P10	1		1
<i>Stegastes adustus</i>	Dusky Damselfish	P10	1		1
<i>Stegastes leucostictus</i>	Beaugregory	P10			1

<i>Stegastes partitus</i>	Bicolor Damselfish	P10	1		
<i>Stegastes planifrons</i>	Threespot Damselfish	P10	1	1	1
<i>Stegastes xanthurus</i>	Cocoa Damselfish	P11	1	1	
POTAMOTRYGONIDAE					
<i>Styracura schmardae</i>	Caribbean Whiptail stingray	P11	1		
PRIACANTHIDAE					
<i>Heteropriacanthus cruentatus</i>	Glasseye Snapper	P11	1	1	
<i>Priacanthus arenatus</i>	Bigeye	P11	1		
SCIAENIDAE					
<i>Eques lanceolatus</i>	Jackknife-fish	P11	1	1	
<i>Eques punctatus</i>	Spotted Drum	P11	1	1	1
<i>Odontoscion dentex</i>	Reef Croaker	P11	1	1	
<i>Pareques lineatus</i>	Southern highhat	P11	1		
SCOMBRIDAE					
<i>Scomberomorus regalis</i>	Cero	P11			1
SCORPAENIDAE					
<i>Pterois volitans</i>	Red Lionfish	P11	1	1	
<i>Scorpaena plumieri</i>	Spotted Scorpionfish	P11	1	1	1
<i>Scorpaenodes caribbaeus</i>	Reef Scorpionfish	P11	1		
<i>Scorpaenodes tredecimspinosus</i>	Deepreef Scorpionfish	P11	1		
SERRANIDAE					
<i>Cephalopholis cruentata</i>	Graysby	P11	1		
<i>Cephalopholis fulva</i>	Coney	P11	1		
<i>Diplectrum bivittatum</i>	Dwarf Sand Perch	P11	1	1	
<i>Hypoplectrus aberrans</i>	Yellowbelly Hamlet	P11	1		
<i>Hypoplectrus affinis</i>	Blue-lip Hamlet	P11	1		
<i>Hypoplectrus guttavarius</i>	Shy Hamlet	P11	1		1
<i>Hypoplectrus nigricans</i>	Black Hamlet	P11	1		1
<i>Hypoplectrus puella</i>	Barred Hamlet	P12	1	1	1
<i>Hypoplectrus randallorum</i>	Tan Hamlet	P12			1
<i>Hypoplectrus unicolor</i>	Butter Hamlet	P12	1	1	1
<i>Hyporthodus niveatus</i>	Snowy Grouper	P12	1		
<i>Liopropoma mowbrayi</i>	Cave Basslet	P12	1		
<i>Liopropoma rubre</i>	Peppermint Basslet	P12	1		
<i>Mycteroperca acutirostris</i>	Western Comb Grouper	P12	1		
<i>Mycteroperca bonaci</i>	Black Grouper	P12	1		
<i>Mycteroperca cidi</i>	Venezuelan Grouper	P12	1		
<i>Mycteroperca interstitialis</i>	Yellowmouth Grouper	P12	1		
<i>Paranthias furcifer</i>	Atlantic Creolefish	P12	1		
<i>Parasphyraenops incisus</i>	Splitfin Bass / Bantam Bass	P12	1		
<i>Pseudogramma gregoryi</i>	Reef Bass	P12	1		
<i>Rypticus saponaceus</i>	Greater Soapfish	P12	1		
<i>Rypticus subbifrenatus</i>	Spotted Soapfish	P12	1		
<i>Schultzea beta</i>	School Bass	P12	1		
<i>Serraniculus pumilio</i>	Pygmy Sea Bass	P12	1		
<i>Serranus annularis</i>	Orangeback Bass	P12	1		
<i>Serranus atrobranchus</i>	Blackear Bass	P12	1		
<i>Serranus baldwini</i>	Lantern Bass	P12	1	1	
<i>Serranus chionaraia</i>	Snow Bass	P12	1		
<i>Serranus flaviventris</i>	Twinspot Bass	P12	1		
<i>Serranus tabacarius</i>	Tobaccofish	P12	1	1	

<i>Serranus tigrinus</i>	Harlequin Bass	P12	1		
<i>Serranus tortugarum</i>	Chalk Bass	P12	1	1	1
SPARIDAE					
<i>Archosargus rhomboidalis</i>	Sea Bream	P12	1		
<i>Diplodus caudimacula</i>	Silver Porgy	P12	1		
SPHYRAENIDAE					
<i>Sphyraena barracuda</i>	Great Barracuda	P12	1		1
<i>Sphyraena borealis</i>	Sennet	P13	1		
SYNGNATHIDAE					
<i>Cosmocampus albirostris</i>	Whitenose Pipefish	P13	1		
<i>Halicampus crinitus</i>	Banded Pipefish	P13	1		
<i>Hippocampus reidi</i>	Longsnout Seahorse	P13	1		1
SYNODONTIDAE					
<i>Synodus intermedius</i>	Sand Diver	P13	1	1	1
<i>Synodus synodus</i>	Red Lizardfish	P13	1		
<i>Trachinocephalus myops</i>	Snakefish	P13	1		
TETRAODONTIDAE					
<i>Canthigaster jamestyeri</i>	Goldface Toby	P13	1		
<i>Canthigaster rostrata</i>	Sharpnose Puffer	P13	1		1
<i>Sphoeroides dorsalis</i>	Marbled Puffer	P13	1		
<i>Sphoeroides spengleri</i>	Bandtail Puffer	P13	1	1	
<i>Sphoeroides testudineus</i>	Checkered Puffer	P13			1
TRIGLIDAE					
<i>Prionotus rubio</i>	Blackwing Searobin	P13	1		
TRIPTERYGIIDAE					
<i>Enneanectes altivelis</i>	Lofty Triplefin	P13	1	1	1
<i>Enneanectes deloachorum</i>	Two-bar Triplefin	P13	1		1
UROTRYGONIDAE					
<i>Urobatis jamaicensis</i>	Yellow Stingray	P13		1	